

COUMARINS FROM 5-*n*-PENTADECYLRESORCINOL AND THE FRIES REACTION OF THEIR ESTERS

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5-Hydroxycoumarin derivatives have been obtained by the interaction of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl methylacetoacetate and ethyl ethylacetoacetate. The Fries reaction of the acetoxy-coumarins in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has been studied.

Rasinski (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1882, *ii*, 26, 59) obtained a ketone by condensing orcinol with glacial acetic acid in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. This ketone later was proved to be 2:6-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone by Ludwinowsky and Tambor (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4047). Shah *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228, 1066; *Nature*, 1938, 142, 163) have brought forward the evidence of γ -substitution in resorcinol derivatives. Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1684; 1935, 628; 1937, 479) observed that certain resacetophenone derivatives underwent γ -substitution. Desai *et al.* (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 8A, 194; 1940, 12A, 391) showed that resacetophenone and orcinol underwent γ -substitution side by side with β -substitution. Orcinol also furnished a case of γ -substitution when condensed with succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (Desai and Shroff, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1941, 10, Part III, 97).

Orcinol undergoes the Pechmann reaction with open-chain as well as cyclic β -ketonic esters, yielding 5-hydroxycoumarins, as observed by Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 99, 1614), and Ahmed and Desai (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 227). We thought it interesting to study the Pechmann reaction of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol as it contains the higher alkyl group, which we hoped would favour γ -substitution. We condensed 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl methylacetoacetate and ethyl ethylacetoacetate to obtain 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives as these dissolved in alkali with a yellow colour. These were characterised by their acetyl and methoxy derivatives. The same coumarins were obtained when polyphosphoric acid was used instead of concentrated sulphuric acid.

The Fries reaction of the esters of hydroxycoumarins was carried out by various workers (Desai *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 185; 1938, 8A, 571; 1941, 14A, 99; 1942, 15A, 11; Shah *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228, 1424; 1939, 1250; Limaye *et al.*, *Rasayanam*, 1936, 20; 1937, 93; 1938, 141; 1939, 187). Desai and Mavani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 25A, 32) have studied the Fries reaction of esters of 7-hydroxy-, 6-hydroxy-, 7:8-dihydroxy- and 6:7-dihydroxy-coumarins. Desai and Bhavsar (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 167) have studied the rearrangement of *p*-toluenesulphonates of 7-hydroxy- and 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. We have studied the Fries reaction of the acetyl derivatives of the coumarins obtained from 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol. The Fries reaction of 4-methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin (I: R=H;

$R_1 = \text{COMe}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$) in presence of three mols. of anhydrous aluminium chloride furnished 4-methyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin (I: $R = -\text{COMe}$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$), the acetyl group migrating to position 6. Similarly 3: 4-dimethyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin (I: $R = \text{H}$; $R_1 = -\text{COMe}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$) and 3-ethyl-4-methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin (I: $R = \text{H}$; $R_1 = -\text{COMe}$; $R_2 = \text{Et}$) afforded 3: 4-dimethyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin (I: $R = -\text{COMe}$; $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$), and 3-ethyl-4-methyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin (I: $R = -\text{COMe}$; $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Et}$) respectively. These products develop a reddish coloration with ferric chloride solution, indicating the *ortho* positions of -OH and COMe groups.

In view of the investigation by Parkhi and Sethna (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 159) we are submitting some of our relevant results. Further work on the reactions of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin.—To 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (3 g.), dissolved in ethyl acetoacetate (2 c.c.), H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c.c.) was gradually added and the mixture left overnight. The mixture was poured over crushed ice, when a solid separated. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol in white shining needles, m.p. 148° , yield quantitative. It shows a greenish coloration with ferric chloride solution and dissolves in dilute alkali, developing a yellow colour. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 10.3. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 77.7; H, 9.9%.)

Polyphosphoric acid (orthophosphoric acid 12 c.c. + P_2O_5 15 g.) was added slowly to 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (3 g.), dissolved in ethyl acetoacetate (3 c.c.). The mixture was heated in an oil bath at $120\text{--}30^\circ$ for 2 hours with stirring and then poured over crushed ice, when a solid separated. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol in shining needles, m.p. 148° .

4-Methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethanol in glistening needles, m.p. 88° . It showed no coloration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 9.9. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 75.7; H, 9.4%.)

4-Methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-methoxycoumarin, prepared by treating the coumarin (0.5 g.) with dimethyl sulphate (5 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate, was crystallised from ethanol in small colorless needles, m.p. 86° . (Found: C, 78.6; H, 10.6. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.0; H, 10.1%.)

4-Methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-benzoyloxycoumarin was prepared by treating the coumarin (0.5 g.) with benzoyl chloride (5 c.c.) in presence of pyridine. It was crystallised from ethanol in shining white needles, m.p. 95° . (Found: C, 78.48; H, 9.63. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 78.40; H, 8.57%.)

3: 4-*Dimethyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin*.—A mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (3 g.), ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (2 c.c.), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c.c.) was kept overnight. It was poured on crushed ice and the product obtained was filtered, dried, and crystallised from dilute ethanol in thin yellowish needles, m.p. 125° . It dissolves in dilute alkali with a yellow colour. (Found: C, 78.60; H, 10.55. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.0; H, 10.0%.)

3: 4-*Dimethyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 85° . (Found: C, 76.5; H, 9.6. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 76.0; H, 9.5%.)

3-*Ethyl-4-methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin*.—A mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (3 g.), ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate (3 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc.) was kept overnight. The product separating on decomposition was filtered off, dried, and crystallised from ethanol in yellowish white

needles, m.p. 135°. It dissolves in dilute alkali with a yellow colour. (Found : C, 78.51 ; H, 10.42. $C_{27}H_{48}O_3$ requires C, 78.25 ; H, 10.05%).

3-Ethyl-4-methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin, prepared as usual, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 95°. (Found : C, 76.25 ; H, 9.39. $C_{28}H_{44}O_4$ requires C, 76.31 ; H, 9.65%).

Fries Migration

4-Methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin: *Formation of 4-Methyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin*.—An intimate mixture of the acetoxycoumarin (2 g.) and $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 4 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 3 hours. The residue, obtained after decomposing the excess of $AlCl_3$ with ice-cold HCl, was purified by alkali. The solid obtained on acidifying the alkaline solution was filtered, dried, and crystallised from dilute ethanol in small colorless needles, m.p. 138°. It develops a reddish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 75.64 ; H, 9.64. $C_{27}H_{40}O_4$ requires C, 75.70 ; H, 9.41%).

3 : 4-Dimethyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin: *Formation of 3 : 4-Dimethyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin*.—The solid obtained on treatment of the relative acetoxycoumarin, as above and purified in the same way, furnished colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 195°. It also gave a similar colour reaction with $FeCl_3$. (Found : C, 76.36 ; H, 9.24. $C_{28}H_{48}O_4$ requires C, 76.0 ; H, 9.50%).

3-Ethyl-4-methyl-7-pentadecyl-5-acetoxycoumarin: *Formation of 3-Ethyl-4-methyl-6-acetyl-7-pentadecyl-5-hydroxycoumarin*.—The relative acetoxycoumarin on Fries migration, as above, furnished colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 198°. It develops a reddish colour with $FeCl_3$. (Found : C, 76.67 ; H, 9.72. $C_{28}H_{44}O_4$ requires C, 76.31 ; H, 9.65%).

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